

Optimisation-based Energy Management System for Hydrogen Integration in a Grid-Connected Microgrid: A Case Study in the Glass Industry

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Abstract

As part of the decarbonisation efforts in high-temperature industries, hydrogen is emerging as a key alternative fuel to reduce overall CO_2 emissions. In Europe, natural gas—composed of more than 90% methane—is currently the predominant fuel for glass industrial furnaces. Integrating hydrogen into this context requires the development of an industrial microgrid for on-site hydrogen production and storage. In this system, electricity is supplied by both the power grid and Renewable Energy Sources (RESs), serving the demands of a PEM electrolyser (ELY) and the electrical load of the furnace. The remaining thermal demand of the furnace is met by a combination of natural gas and hydrogen. The optimisation presented in this study foresees the Energy Management System (EMS) approach: for this industrial microgrid layout, the minimisation of operational costs of all the components is performed on an hourly time step, based on glass production, RES generation forecasts and gas and electricity price projections for the following 24 hours. The effectiveness of the system is proven by means of the microgrid simulation over a time period of 20 days, using real data from the industry. The optimisation model accounts for low-emission targets and furnace load constraints. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the flexibility and feasibility of hydrogen integration in a glass industrial setting.

1 Introduction

In 2018, the European Commission presented the "Green Deal", the European strategy to reduce greenhouse gases (GHG) targets by the decarbonisation of energy, transportation, residential, and industry sectors [1]. Following this path, climate neutrality is expected to be achieved by 2050 for all European countries participating in the deal. Among all, the energy production sector and the industry are the most impactful [2]. In 2022, the total amount of CO_2 emissions related to the industry accounted for 9.2 Gt, representing around the 20% of the total global emissions [3]. Having the energy-intensive industries the highest environmental impact in terms of emissions, their production systems have reached high efficiencies but are still fossil fuel dependent: around 95% of the high-temperature heat is supplied by fossil fuel combustion or combustible by-products. The steel, iron, glass and chemicals production are considered high-temperature industries, since the operational processes largely overcome 400°C. [4]. To drastically reduce GHG emissions, the main solutions proposed are the electrification of the sectors and the use of hydrogen as an energy source to fill the gap between electrification and the hard-to-abate sectors. Hydrogen indeed can be used as a feedstock, fuel, energy carrier and energy storage medium. The European Commission adopted Energy System Integration and hydrogen strategies to accelerate the transition to more integrated and clean energy systems. For this purpose, the Clean

Hydrogen Joint Undertaking aims to accelerate the development and deployment of European value and chain for safe and sustainable clean hydrogen technology, supporting notably small and medium enterprises towards climate neutrality [5]. The actual use of hydrogen covers 60% of ammonia production, 30% of methanol and 10% Direct Reduction Iron (DRI) in the iron and steel subsector, where the industrial hydrogen production was responsible for 680 Mt of CO_2 emissions in 2022, with China as the main hydrogen consumer. Since more than 90% of hydrogen production relies on fossil fuels, one third of the industrial hydrogen production capacity needs to be low-emission by 2030, in order to meet the emission reduction objectives. Projects to produce more than 600 kt of low-emission hydrogen are under construction or have taken Final Investment Decision (FID): the majority are concentrated 40% in Europe, following 28% in China and 24% Middle East [6]. To reach the Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenarios means to significantly increase the production of hydrogen to supply the actual demand as feedstock, fuel, energy carrier, and energy storage medium, drastically dropping the CO_2 emissions. The installed electrolyser capacity should reach 850 GW, for a total production of 212 Mt by 2030 and an electricity supply of 3850 TWh [7]. Hydrogen can be a beneficiary of flexibility on the demand side and on variability on the renewable energy sources on the energy supply side [8].

Fig. 1 Microgrid layout: at Node A, the PV and grid withdrawal supply the electrolyser, the electric load, and the electrolyser; Nodes B and C relate to the hydrogen side; the furnace load is supplied by fuel mixture at Node D and electricity at Node A

1.1 The glass industry case

The glass industry is an energy-intensive industry, characterised to be extremely diverse. It can be divided into subsectors: container glass, flat glass, special glass and glass fibres. Around 80% of the global industry is accounted by container and flat glass, where the former covers 47% of CO_2 emissions and the latter 33%. Although the glass demand is growing 1.5-2% annually, the energy demand decreases of 12% between 2015 and 2030. In order to reduce the energy consumption, the optimisation of the operation or design parameters of the melting furnace is required. The operating temperature between 1200 and 1600 °C. The different phases are collecting raw materials, batch preparation, melting and fining, forming, post-forming, and finishing [9]. The majority of energy is required by the glass melting furnace, considering a continuously operated melting furnace. The classification of the furnaces follows the type of energy-carrier, the direction of the flames, and the type of heat recovery. A total of 75% of global container glass companies use regenerative EP furnaces, while 90% of the melting furnaces installed worldwide in the flat glass industry are constituted by regenerative SP furnaces, for melting capacities between 100 and 450 tonnes of glass per day. An alternative is oxy-fuel melting furnaces. The electric melting presents higher efficiency compared to fossil fuels, and lower investment costs, while it strongly depends on the fluctuation of the current electricity price. Hybrid melting smooths the disadvantages of electrically- and fossil fuel-fired furnaces [9]. The different decarbonization options are classified in terms of energy and material, including combustion gases and oxygen preheating, as well as batch and cullet preheating. Thermochemical heat recovery, Organic Rankine Cycle, and Thermo-electric generator are few of the Heat-to-Power solutions taken into account for this sector. The glass process impact is evaluated in terms of CO_2 emissions: for 1 kg of glass in a gas-fired furnace, 0.6 kg of CO_2 is produced. The share from fossil fuel

combustion accounts for 0.45 kg, while 0.15 kg comes from the dissolution of carbonate raw. Introducing hydrogen is a good solution for the decarbonisation of this industry [10]. Hydrogen can reduce CO_2 emissions, enhance energy efficiency and maintain furnace longevity. It is moreover easy to integrate into the existing furnace setup [11]. In this context, the purpose of this article is to analyse the integration of the hydrogen production in a grid-connected microgrid, focusing on costs and GHG emissions during the continuous operation. The introduction of hydrogen as a fuel in the context of the glass industry may show the reduction of CO_2 emissions. A cost analysis is conducted to compare different Scenarios among optimised solutions.

2 Modelling of the system components

For the production and storage of hydrogen and the complete supply of the electric and furnace load, a microgrid is taken into account. The microgrid system consists of an electrical withdrawal from the grid, a photovoltaic (PV) source and a hydrogen grid with a connection to the Natural Gas (NG) grid, as shown in Fig. 1. The electrical side foresees the combination of a PV source, an electricity grid supply, and an electric load representing the industry consumption. The mix of electricity supplies a PEM electrolyser, the compressor in the storage unit, and the electrical load at the furnace. The hydrogen flow produced is split to feed the furnace and the storage unit, the latter composed of a hydrogen tank and a compressor. The hydrogen can be mixed with the NG supplied from the gas grid: the burner injects the fuel mixture into the furnace.

2.1 PV, Grid supply and NG purchase

The PV system is modelled using a steady-state generator model, where all the data are effectively collected from the PV plant adjacent to the glassmaker. The active power generated $P_{PVplant}(t)$ is defined in [kW] for each time t of the studied

period. To avoid overproduction of PV source, in (1) the curtailment of the electricity excess is ensured, where $P_{PV}(t)$ stands for the variable total PV power requested in the optimisation.

$$P_{PV}(t) \leq P_{PVplant}(t) \quad (1)$$

The grid is considered a source of electricity, where no excess electricity from the PV supply is injected. The cost of the electricity withdrawal from the grid is reported in (2), where $P_{grid}(t)$ is the power in [kW] and $p_{ele}(t)$ is the electricity price [€/kWh] at each time step Δt in [h].

$$C_{grid}(t) = P_{grid}(t) * p_{ele}(t) * \Delta t \quad (2)$$

As shown in Fig. 1, Node D foresees a connection to the natural gas grid that supplies the furnace load. The total demand of NG is expressed by the variable $P_{NG}(t)$ in [kW]. The associated cost is calculated in (3), where $p_{NG}(t)$ represents the market price in [€/kWh] for each time step Δt .

$$C_{NG}(t) = P_{NG}(t) * p_{NG}(t) * \Delta t \quad (3)$$

The direct emission addressed to the NG combustion are evaluated by the formula (4), where LHV_{NG} is the Lower Heating Value of NG in [kWh/Nm³], ρ_{NG} is the NG density and $R_{MOLERate}$ corresponds to the combustion mole balance: from the combustion equation, $R_{MOLERate}$ is the ratio between the carbon dioxide and methane mole mass. The indirect emissions quantity related to the grid is calculated in (5), where ECI represents the energy carbon intensity coefficient in [kgCO₂/kWh].

$$M_{CO_2direct}(t) = \frac{P_{NG}(t) * \rho_{NG}}{LHV_{NG}} * R_{MOLERate} \quad (4)$$

$$M_{CO_2indirect}(t) = P_{grid}(t) * ECI * \Delta t \quad (5)$$

In (6) and (7), the cost of the emissions is obtained by multiplying the amount of carbon dioxide $M_{CO_2direct}(t)$ and $M_{CO_2indirect}(t)$ with the emission price p_{CO_2} in [€/kgCO₂].

$$C_{emissions_{NG}}(t) = M_{CO_2direct}(t) * p_{CO_2} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{emissions_{grid}}(t) = M_{CO_2indirect}(t) * p_{CO_2} \quad (7)$$

The burner is supposed to inject the fuel or the fuel mixture (hydrogen+NG) in the furnace with an efficiency of η_{BURN} . In (8), $P_{nodeD}(t)$ represents the quantity of NG or mixture of NG and hydrogen in terms of [kW] and $P_{FURN}(t)$ is the power requested at the furnace to be supplied.

$$P_{FURN}(t) = \eta_{BURN} * P_{nodeD}(t) \quad (8)$$

The assumption considers one burner feeding the furnace with the fuel mixture.

Fig. 2 Multistage model for the electrolyser. The three stages are represented by three circles; to each transition between stages a cost is associated

2.2 Furnace and Electric load

At Node A reported in Fig. 1, the electric load is split into two different entities: the electric load of the plant is represented with $P_{elePLANT}(t)$, while the electric load at the furnace $P_{eleFURN}(t)$ represents the electric contribution to the total consumption at the furnace $P_{FURN}(t)$. This electrical contribution at the furnace is also named "Electric Boost" (E-Boost) and is generally constrained as a part of the furnace load, as shown in (9).

$$\%_{min} * P_{FURN}(t) \leq P_{eleFURN}(t) \leq \%_{max} * P_{FURN}(t) \quad (9)$$

2.3 Electrolyser and Storage Unit

The inlet power of the electrolyser $P_{elyIN}(t)$ is constrained with rated power P_{rated} evaluated in [kW] in (10).

$$P_{elyIN}(t) \leq P_{rated} \quad (10)$$

The efficiency η_{eff} characterises the electrolyser type relating the inlet power and outlet power $P_{elyOUT}(t)$ in [kW] as shown in (11).

$$P_{elyOUT}(t) = \eta_{eff} * P_{elyIN}(t) \quad (11)$$

In (12), the ramp up P_{RAMP} in [kW/h] is considered as a percentage of rated power to limit the variation of hydrogen production along time.

$$|P_{elyOUT}(t) - P_{elyOUT}(t-1)| = P_{RAMP} \quad (12)$$

For this work, the estimation of the water purchase feeding the electrolyser and the sale of the oxygen are not considered in the cost balance. The multistage model associates a cost for each behaviour of transition and state between the ON, stand-by (STB) and OFF states. In Fig. 2 a concise representation of the switch among the stages is reported. The binary variables $\delta_{ON}(t)$, $\delta_{STB}(t)$, and $\delta_{OFF}(t)$ are defined in the range [0, 1], so that equal to one if the electrolyser is in that state; equal to zero if not. In (13), the state variables are related to the state power or power range: in working conditions, the electrolyser power

is $P_{elyIN}(t)$, while the STB power is defined in (14).

$$P_{elyIN}(t) = P_{MAX} * \delta_{ON}(t) + P_{STB} * \delta_{STB}(t) + P_{OFF} * \delta_{OFF}(t) \quad (13)$$

$$P_{elySTB}(t) = P_{STB} * \delta_{STB}(t) \quad (14)$$

To define the one state at the time, (15) imposes the sum of state variables equal to one.

$$\delta_{ON}(t) + \delta_{STB}(t) + \delta_{OFF}(t) = 1 \quad (15)$$

The transition variables $\sigma_{\alpha}^{\beta}(t)$ are defined as follows for each possible transition between ON, STB, and OFF states: for each, it is related to the previous state (16), to the current state (17) and to the combination of both to avoid overlapment (18)

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^{\beta}(t) \leq \delta^{\alpha}(t-1) \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^{\beta}(t) \leq \delta^{\beta}(t) \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha}^{\beta}(t) \geq \delta^{\alpha}(t-1) + \delta^{\beta}(t) - 1 \quad (18)$$

Where $\alpha, \beta \in \{ON, STB, OFF\}$, $\sigma_{\alpha}^{\beta}t \in [0, 1]$ and α represents the previous state and β the following state for all the state combinations. The ON state describes a state where power is consumed following hydrogen production. In the STB mode, hydrogen is not produced, but there is a minimum consumption in terms of costs to sustain the operating temperature and pressure for the startup. In the OFF state, no hydrogen is produced, with no power consumption associated. The storage unite is composed by a compressor and a storage tank: the hydrogen flow $P_{compIN}(t)$ in [kW] is compressed with specific consumption L_{comp} in [kJ/kg_{H₂}] as reported in (19), with $P_{compgrid}(t)$ as power requested for the compression and LHV_{H_2} as lower heating value of hydrogen.

$$P_{compgrid}(t) = \frac{P_{compIN}(t) * L_{comp}}{LHV_{H_2} * 3600} \quad (19)$$

The mass conservation equation is guaranteed in (20), where all the compressed hydrogen flow $P_{tankIN}(t)$ enters the storage tank.

$$P_{compIN}(t) = P_{tankIN}(t) \quad (20)$$

The energy balance is expressed defining the State of Charge (SOC) $SOC(t)$ as adimensional value in (21), where the total storage capacity is C_{tank} in [kWh] and $P_{tankIN}(t)$ and $P_{tankOUT}(t)$ are inlet and outlet power values in [kW] with η_{charge} and $\eta_{discharge}$ as efficiencies of charge and discharge, respectively.

$$SOC(t) = SOC(t-1) + \frac{P_{tankIN}(t) * \Delta t * \eta_{charge}}{C_{tank}} - \frac{P_{tankOUT}(t) * \Delta t}{C_{tank} * \eta_{discharge}} \quad (21)$$

The SOC is constrained in range among a minimum and maximum values SOC_{MIN} and SOC_{MAX} as shown in (22).

$$SOC_{MIN} \leq SOC(t) \leq SOC_{MAX} \quad (22)$$

3 Methodology

This methodology is based on optimisation of mixed integer linear programming (MILP) to minimise total costs related to the operation of the energy balance of the plant: for this purpose, the analysis involves electric energy supply, hydrogen production and storage, emission costs, and furnace load provision, without considering processes related to the logistics and maintenance of glass production. The problem is presented in (23), where the objective function $f(x)$ is minimised subject to the equality $h(x)$ and inequality $g(x)$ constraints.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \quad & f(x) && \text{Objective function} \\ \text{subject to} \quad & h(x) = 0 && \text{Equality constraints} \\ & g(x) \leq 0 && \text{Inequality constraints} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The EMS approach is applied to perform the optimisation by solving the problem considering forecasts of the following rolling horizon for PV data, NG and electricity price and future load. The outputs address the Power Set-Points and the operational costs of all the energy assets, and the direct and indirect emissions quantities. Under the flexibility requirements, the The Fig. 3 shows the flowchart of the methodology. For the solution the package CVXPY is used in Pyomo, where CPLEX is used as a solver. For the case study, the analysis considers the total time required to simulate 20 days with a time step of 1 hour, where the forecast horizon is 24 hours.

3.1 Objective function

All the costs mentioned in Section 2 are summed in (24), establishing the objective function. The scope of the optimisation is the minimisation of these costs, by considering constraints defined by the problem:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{TOTopt}(t) = & C_{grid}(t) + C_{NG}(t) \\ & + C_{emissions_{grid}}(t) + C_{emissions_{NG}}(t) \\ & + C_{ELYstate}(t) + C_{ELYtrans}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

3.2 Constraints

Most of the constraints are related to asset modelling: all assets of the system must be considered and, for each of them, the constraints correspond to the equations presented in Section 2. The power flow for electric and furnace loads must be supplied each hour. Then, the power balances must be ensured, as imposed by the power flow. The Node A collects the electrical sources of PV and the electrical grid, so that the electrolyser, the electric load and the E-Boost at the furnace are satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{PV}(t) + P_{grid} = & P_{elyIN}(t) + P_{elySTB}(t) + P_{eleFUR}(t) \\ & + P_{elePLANT}(t) + P_{compIN}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The hydrogen flow produced at the electrolyser is split to send one part directly to the furnace, while the other part is stored

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the methodology

into the storage unit, as shown in (26) at Node B.

$$P_{ely_{OUT}}(t) = P_{ely_{OUTBURNER}}(t) + P_{compIN}(t) \quad (26)$$

In (27), the hydrogen flow directly feeding the furnace is joined to the flow from the storage unit.

$$P_{ely_{OUTBURNER}}(t) + P_{tank_{OUT}}(t) = P_{nodeC}(t) \quad (27)$$

The mixture of NG and hydrogen occurs at Node D, as shown in (28).

$$P_{nodeC}(t) + P_{NG}(t) = P_{nodeD}(t) \quad (28)$$

3.3 Indicators

To help the comparison among different scenarios considered, the mass of CO_2 from direct and indirect emissions are evaluated as expressed in (4) and (5). The optimised total cost in (24) is useful to analyse the evolution of the operation in economic terms each hour of the optimisation. The relative cost difference RCD is calculate by the formula in (29), where $C_{ref}(t)$ is a reference value for the total optimised cost with respect to the considered $C(t)$

$$RCD = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_{ref}(t) - C(t)}{C_{ref}(t)} \quad (29)$$

The RCD is adimensional value: if positive, it shows that the total optimised cost is lower than the reference one. If negative, it means that the overall cost is higher compared to the reference value $C_{ref}(t)$.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Case study

This study focuses on a real case of a glassmaker of container glass in a member state of the European Union (EU). All the input data of PV, electric load, and furnace load are considered by this industrial case in the time period from 06/09/24 to 26/09/24. The PV power varies between 0 and 78 kW, depending on the solar resource of the plant location. The total PV

contribution to the energy balance addresses 2 MWh/week. The supply of NG occurs according to the relative EU member state market: the NG price is considered fixed for the third quarter of the year 2024 at $p_{NG}(t) = 0.0617 \text{ €/kWh}$. The price of electricity $p_{ele}(t)$ is referred to the same time period of the year 2024. Fig. 4 compares the price behaviour of electricity and NG for the considered time period. Following [16], the direct

Fig. 4. Price comparison between grid electricity and NG

emission are evaluated by the formula (4), where $p_{CO_2} = 0.075 \text{ €/kgCO}_2$. ECI represents the quantity of indirect emissions for the generation of the the amount of energy available on the grid. A coefficient of 219 $\text{gCO}_2\text{eq/kWh}$ according to the European Union's Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is considered [16].

The electric load related to the plant reaches around 73 MWh/week, while the load at the furnace consists of 291 MWh/week. The actual fuel used to supply is natural gas. The E-Boost covers between 8% and 12% of the total furnace load, reaching an average consumption of 26 MWh/week. In general, the E-Boost is important for increasing the quality of the batch: a fully electricity-based solution is feasible for furnaces

operating at lower loads. For the dimensions of the considered case, hydrogen is the recommended fuel. The Fig. 5 represents the load evolution related to the thermal and E-Boost at the furnace and the electric load: while the furnace load presents mostly value zero in the first 5 days, the electric load of the plant remains mostly constant along the 20 days horizon.

Fig. 5 The composition of the load divided into thermal and E-boost at the furnace and electric load of the plant

The electrolyser model considered is a proton exchange membrane (PEM) with rated power 2.5 MW. The Table 1 resumes the specificities adopted.

Table 1 Specificities for the electrolyser model

Specificity	Value	
P_{rated}	2.5	[MW]
η_{eff}	65	[%]
P_{RAMP}	40	[% P_{rated} /h]

Table 2 resumes the values for the transition and state costs from [12] and [13], where the state costs are referred to the rated power. The cost model of the electrolyser foresees a lower STB-to-ON transition compared to the OFF-to-ON or OFF-to-STB transitions, as in the STB state, the device stacks don't produce hydrogen but consume a low amount of power: the meaning of this action is to mitigate the possible degradation of membrane components. For this reason, the value of c_{OFFSTB} is set two orders of magnitude higher than the OFF-to-ON, to dissuade the start-up condition.

The initial moment foresees the electrolyser at the ON state at the maximum production allowed in (11) by the efficiency. The hydrogen flow produced by the electrolyser is compressed from 30 to 200 bar, with specific consumption L_{comp} of 4 MJ/kg H_2 as reported in (19) and (20) with LHV_{H_2} as lower heating value of hydrogen [15]. The total storage capacity is assumed 100 kg of hydrogen [14] and balance reported in (21), with a SOC between 10% and 90% represented in (22) and an initial

Table 2 Reference power values for multistage model of the electrolyser

Reference power	Value	
P_0	0	[%ratedpower]
P_{STB}	1	[%ratedpower]
$P_{ON} - P_{MAX}$	10-100	[%ratedpower]
c_{ON}	0.0334	€/MWh
c_{STB}	0.0042	€/MWh
c_{OFF}	0.00	€/MWh
c_{STBON}	0.00	€
c_{ONSTB}	0.00	€
c_{STBOFF}	0.00	€
c_{OFFSTB}	1000	€
c_{OFFON}	31.25	€
c_{ONOFF}	0.00	€

value of 50%. where $\eta_{charge} = \eta_{discharge} = 1$ as efficiencies of charge and discharge. The operational costs of the compressor and tank are considered zero. The operational costs of PV plant, compressor, and storage tank are considered negligible during this analysis.

4.2 Emission analysis

The comparison of four different scenarios may help to understand the behaviour of the model and the cost analysis. In Scenario 0, the furnace load is supplied by NG, while Scenario 1 foresees the contribution of E-Boost. With the same share of E-Boost, Scenario 2 and Scenario 3 introduce hydrogen into the furnace, with a minimum of 5% of the load in the former and a minimum of 68% in the latter. Scenario 3 shows the maximum quantity of hydrogen contribution that the electrolyser with this size may supply to the load. As shown in Fig. 6, the contribu-

Fig. 6 Share of energy vector used to supply the furnace load divided by scenario

tion of E-Boost is always the same quantity. In Scenario 2 and Scenario 3, it is assumed that the fuel mixture is injected by

one burner adapted to the fuel content. The share of hydrogen reaches around 28 MWh/week and around 198 MWh/week for Scenario 3 and Scenario 4, respectively. The emission analysis highlights how Scenario 0 addresses the highest CO_2 production: in terms of direct emissions, it corresponds to fully NG combustion to supply the furnace load; the indirect emissions correspond to the electrical withdrawal from the grid to supply the electric load with RES supply. The general trend of an increase in indirect emissions and a decrease in direct emissions is explained by the effective drop in NG consumption and rise of electric consumption, due to E-Boost and electrolyser supply. Scenario 1 foresees an increase of 36% in the indirect emissions, since the E-Boost load contribution is covered by the electric Node A, instead of NG combustion. The introduction of hydrogen drastically reduces the direct contribution of 18% in Scenario 2 and 75% for Scenario 3, with respect to Scenario 0. In terms of indirect emissions, hydrogen production addresses a growth of 98% and 468% for Scenario 2 and Scenario 3, respectively.

Fig. 7 Comparison between NG direct and grid indirect emissions within the scenarios

4.3 Optimised cost analysis

The minimisation of the objective function reported in (24) is performed at each time step, stating a valuable result for the optimised costs. By comparing the results in Fig. 8 with Fig. 5, it is evident how the electric and furnace loads affect the cost evolution: in the first five days, the optimised costs are low, since the supplied loads present low values. The RCD for Scenario 2 and Scenario 3 are 3.88% and 3.80%, respectively: for these two cases, the overall optimised cost is lower than the cost in Scenario 0. However, some exceptions are present, since the electricity purchase has to be performed even if an inconvenient electricity price, due to the imposition of a minimum share of hydrogen and E-Boost. The combination of NG and hydrogen provides the system with a good flexibility capacity: having two sources of energy content, it gives the possibility to ponder and

choose the one that is more economically convenient or with lower environmental impact. In the case of hydrogen grid, the storage unit also plays a strategic role: the hydrogen production can occur even when there is no need to supply the furnace. The storage unit can be filled by taking advantage of the lower electricity cost, so it can be consumed when needed. In Scenario 1, the RCD corresponds to -1.87%, attesting to generally higher cost values due to forced electricity purchase to supply the E-Boost.

Fig. 8 Comparison between optimised cost within the scenarios

4.4 Electrolyser behaviour

In Fig. 9, the electrolyser behaviour is addressed from day 7 to day 10, where the load behaviour is representative of the operation of the plant. The comparison between the electricity and NG prices highlights when the former is lower than the latter: for these time periods, it is more convenient to withdraw electricity from the grid and produce hydrogen. The optimisation takes into account the load supply and the SOC level: the hydrogen produced may be directed to the furnace or can refill the storage tank, balancing the load, the charge's state and electricity cost.

5 Conclusion

This paper analyses the role of hydrogen in the decarbonisation of the glass industry. As one of the sector of the high-temperature industry, it is characterised by high levels of emissions, since nowadays loads are supplied by carbon-based fuels. The methodology presented in this work aims to provide an evaluation of the optimised costs for the hydrogen integration in these systems, with an EMS approach for an optimisation of a forecast of 24 hours. In the optimisation, operational costs of electrolyser are minimised combined with the purchase of electricity from the grid and natural gas, and direct and indirect emissions costs. The results show that for the

Fig. 9 Behaviour of the electrolyser operation compared with the electricity price evolution. The ON, OFF, and STB states are represented by 0 and 1 values

case of hydrogen integration, there is a great reduction in terms of costs and emissions. Despite the introduction of hydrogen implies an increase in indirect emissions, the overall emission rate foresees a drop. Moreover, better results can be achieved if the share of RES is increased in the electric mix. The storage unit provides high flexibility of the system. Finally, the operation of the electrolyser is studied by a multistage model, where the operation is related to the price of electricity and natural gas. By associating a cost for each state and transition, the operating behaviour follows variable loads and optimisation constraints.

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